

Submission Template for ACM Papers

Lost in Translation

What is at stake when social values become technical properties for designing principled algorithms

First Author's Name, Initials, and Last name*

First author's affiliation, an Institution with a very long name, xxxx@gmail.com

Second Author's Name, Initials, and Last Name

Second author's affiliation, possibly the same institution, xxxx@gmail.com

Value-based frameworks are rapidly becoming the primary source of guidelines for developing principled technologies. While these frameworks, and the values they promote, have contributed to address emerging challenges sprawling from the relentless algorithmic retrofitting of everyday life, they often fail to account for the unanticipated consequences of this transition. To strengthen these frameworks, critical scholars have stressed the need to incorporate new values that represent the experiences of users rather than the intentions of developers. Although the fidelity of this translation process is crucial for supporting a social turn in the value-proposition of algorithms, scarce attention has been placed on exploring how values extracted from use practices are reinterpreted and appropriated as they become part of development practices. The research presented in this paper addresses this gap by examining how researchers developing assistive technologies for the ageing population conceptualize, translate, and operationalize the value of Care as a design guideline.

CCS CONCEPTS • Human-centered computing • Human computer interaction (HCI) • Empirical studies in HCI

Additional Keywords and Phrases: Value-based frameworks, AI Ethics, Critical Algorithm Studies, moral values, VSD

ACM Format:

~~First Author's Name, Initials, and Last Name, Second Author's Name, Initials, and Last Name, and Third Author's Name, Initials, and Last Name. 2018. The Title of the Paper: ACM Conference Proceedings Manuscript Submission Template: This is the subtitle of the paper, this document both explains and embodies the submission format for authors using Word. In Woodstock '18: ACM Symposium on Neural Gaze Detection, June 03–05, 2018, Woodstock, NY. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 10 pages. NOTE: This block will be automatically generated when manuscripts are processed after acceptance.~~

1 INTRODUCTION

The use of value-based frameworks as a strategy for designing principled algorithms has become widely embraced across the HCI community^[1]. Simply put, value-based frameworks are sets of theoretical and methodological guidelines aimed at helping computer scientists, engineers, and designers integrate human values into technological development processes^[2]. Despite the increasing role that these frameworks play in how algorithms become part of everyday life, there are well-

* Place the footnote text for the author (if applicable) here.

known challenges that question the extent to which these frameworks are ethically and meaningfully shaping technology, particularly concerning whose values are deemed relevant to inform these frameworks and who gets to make those decisions [3,4]. The need to address these and related gaps in the use of value-based frameworks created the necessary momentum for a social turn in HCI research [5-9], particularly in the context of producing the theory and methods needed for empirically approaching human-algorithm interactions and identifying which values are relevant for the people experiencing these technologies, and their outcomes, as part of daily life [10,11].

The social turn in the critical scholarship community has been invaluable for highlighting the need to diversify the values supporting the most relied-upon value-based frameworks in HCI research and putting non-technical values, such as sustainable, inclusive, and fair -- hereon "social values" -- into circulation. However, little attention has been paid to tracing the fidelity with which the meaning and purpose of social values are transmitted across the different research, design and engineering stages involved in the development of algorithm-driven technologies. The fidelity with which social values are communicated across development stages and formalised as design guidelines matters because, for the experiences of people with algorithm-driven technologies to remain part of the conversations that precede the design of algorithms, social values need to stay rooted in the experiences of users rather than developers [12-14].

We address this gap by tracing how the social value of *care* is conceptualised and operationalised by researchers of a European-based research centre working on developing assistive technologies for the ageing population. Through interviews and participant observation conducted over one month, we mapped the different research and development stages involved in the translation of care from a social value into a design guideline, how the meaning and purpose of care as a social value is reinterpreted and appropriated alongside these stages, and with what implications for the design of principled algorithms. The contribution of this research is twofold. On the one hand, we provide relevant insights for critically approaching the practice of using social values to align researchers, guide development processes, and certify algorithmic behaviour. On the other hand, we extend current critiques of value-based frameworks by shifting attention beyond questions of how social values should be selected and implemented to ask instead, *why* values? We begin with a brief overview of why and how social values are used in the design of principled algorithms. Following this, we present our case study and insights from the field research. We finish with a discussion of what is at stake when social values, such as *care*, become detached from context and used as design guidelines.

2 VALUE-BASED FRAMEWORKS

In the context of HCI, contemporary applications of value-based frameworks as a strategy to develop "socially aware algorithms" [15] build on the theory and methods first proposed by Friedman and Kahn [16] under the concept of value-sensitive design (VSD). Simply put, value-sensitive design is a methodology that seeks to design technology that "*accounts for human values in a principled and comprehensive manner throughout the design process*" [17, p. 14]. While the notion that things—from trinkets to complex technologies—can become embedded with human values as they move through social practices is a well-established phenomenon in anthropology and STS literature [18,19] the proposition that such values could be purposefully embedded into technologies through design decisions rather than use practices was taken up by technology developers seeking to address the emerging, mostly unanticipated challenges of the rapid transition of algorithmic technologies from industry to public applications [20,21].

Alongside this transition, and in order to operationalise VSD approaches, researchers and developers had to agree on specific sets of social values that could represent their ethical, technological and market interests. With new markets and applications for algorithms growing exponentially, so did the lists of values – from autonomous, beneficent, and explainable to privacy, efficiency and trust – which became categorised and grouped within larger value-based frameworks

[22]. These frameworks aimed to translate the somewhat open-to-interpretation nature of VSD processes into governance strategies, such as laws, guidelines and policies that public and private developers can refer to when designing new algorithm-driven services and products [23]. In their current form, value-based frameworks claim to provide a “constructive tool that enables and supports the realisation of specific desired values in the design and development of new technologies” [21].

Popular value-based frameworks such as human-centred AI [24], ethical AI [25], AI4SG [26] and FAccT – fairness, accountability and transparency – [27] have been praised for bringing to the fore AI development practices that, purposefully or not, lead to algorithmic decision-making that negatively impacts the lives of users [28,29]. At the same time, the capacity of value-based frameworks to “incorporate in a quantitative, measurable, verifiable manner many of the ethical values we care about as individuals and as a society” [15, p. 18] has been subject to substantial scrutiny. Yet, scrutinising the provenance, underpinning epistemology and limitations of value-based frameworks has not decreased their popularity or prevented new frameworks from emerging. In contrast, it created the momentum for more inclusive frameworks to emerge, such as Black in AI [30], Indigenous AI [31] and more-than-human AI [32], which have extended the impact of value-based frameworks to account for the realities of minority and disenfranchised communities [33,34].

3 RELATED WORK

As value-based frameworks continue to grow in number and diversity, researchers have raised concerns in two main areas. One area focuses on the challenges of integrating ethical analysis into engineering practices [35], particularly the extent to which value-based frameworks offer the necessary guidelines to help programmers translate human values into algorithmic behaviour [36]. According to Morley and colleagues [37], guidelines tend to be too narrow yet not concrete enough, which promotes top-down dynamics that often lead to developers questioning why they are being told to use (a specific set of) values [38]. Yet, to a greater extent, guidelines tend to be vague and flexible, which contributes to the current widespread lack of consensus across researchers and organisations on what social values mean and what is their purpose in the context of technology [39], which in turn can lead to value-washing practices [40].

The second area concerns the social values being used as design guidelines. Researchers have warned about the lack of diversity amongst the narrow number of researchers and developers who get to decide which social values will guide how algorithms interact with vastly diverse groups of people, as well as whose values are deemed relevant to provide the ethical backbone of value-based frameworks [3,4]. In addition, as the sets of values that predominantly inform the production of value-based frameworks begin to broaden, the technical values proposed early on by computer scientists and engineers, such as autonomy and nonmaleficence, have come under scrutiny, with researchers raising doubts about the extent to which these values can meaningfully guide the decision-making processes of algorithms that will operate in social rather than industrial contexts [41,42].

Current gaps in the use of value-based frameworks have raised the need for more empirical research on human-algorithm interactions to identify social values currently missing from value-based frameworks [43]. This approach aims to reduce the risk of producing algorithm-driven technologies that are “ineffective, inaccurate, and sometimes dangerously misguided when they enter the societal context” [5, p. 59]. However, and to a higher degree than values that emerged from technical challenges, research shows that values extracted from social contexts tend to be undertheorized from a philosophical perspective [44], often leading to the meaning and purpose of values representing everyday life open to the interpretation of different stakeholders across the production pipeline of algorithm-driven technologies [45–47].

Critical approaches to the use of value-based frameworks for the development of principled technologies have led to increasing interest amongst HCI researchers in exploring which values people want to see represented in algorithms [48]

and providing the necessary guidelines to help engineers and computer scientists embed social values into code ^[49]. Still, it is unclear if social values, which are meant to bring the experiences of people with algorithms into the conversations that precede their programming, are fulfilling their task as researchers attempt to operationalise them across diverse production stages. This paper positions the challenges of translating values into design guidelines to scrutinise the fidelity with which social values undergo this transformation.

4 CONTEXT OF STUDY: CARE-DRIVEN TECHNOLOGIES

The research took place in a European-based Academic research centre, which we will refer to as the *Institution*. The Institution began operations in the last five years through funding provided by a private company offering services related to retirement, life insurance and pension investments. Within the broader context of care provision, the mission of the Institution is to address challenges related to independent living, dignity and quality of life for ageing adults (65 years of age and older) living in their own homes or supported care environments. For this purpose, the Institution focuses on developing personalised “care technologies” enabled by data science, artificial intelligence, and robotics, such as non-invasive monitoring, health sensors and mobility technologies. To develop these assistive technologies in a principled and ethical manner, the Institution is conducting empirical research aimed at identifying what care means for the ageing population and how care can be operationalised as a guiding value for designing care-driven technologies.

Most of the 60-plus researchers in the Institution are employed at three major universities and represent diverse fields, including medicine and other health-related professions, as well as life sciences, engineering, informatics, and social and data sciences. While the Institution has a multidisciplinary composition, researchers with similar training and experience are grouped into seven interlinking work packages (WP) focusing on distinct stages and challenges for developing care technologies. This structure builds on the premise that, in increasing order, each WPs findings will provide scaffolding for the work of the next. For this investigation, we engaged researchers from three consecutive work packages that we will refer to as A, B and C:

- WP-A is composed of social scientists who use participatory and ethnographic approaches and methods to understand the diverse places, practices, and feelings that the ageing population identifies with the concept of care, particularly those that take place outside spaces traditionally associated with care and medical services.
- WP-B comprises data scientists focused on developing risk prediction and identification models through free-text and unstructured patient-generated data. The main goal of the WP is to create more efficient ways of identifying practices and situations that could benefit from care-driven technologies.
- WP-C is composed of engineers tasked with programming and developing care-driven technologies based on the needs and requirements identified by WPs A and B, as well as based on their own research and understanding of these challenges.

While the Institution intended that WP-A would provide empirical accounts of care for WPs B and C to translate into design guidelines, the mostly homogenous composition of each WP has challenged their ability to meaningfully engage with each other's work. Researchers on WP-A have become aware of this challenge, raising concerns about the extent to which the experiences that the ageing population associates with the value of care are being meaningfully integrated into the development processes of technical work packages. With this challenge as a point of departure, the focus of our investigation concerns tracing the different understandings and uses of the concept of care that co-exist across work packages A, B and C, the degree to which notions of care emerging from empirical research are being reinterpreted and

appropriated as they move from social to technical work packages, and how these dynamics condition the use of care as a guiding value for the design of assistive technologies.

5 METHODS

To explore the use of care as a design guideline across work packages, the first author conducted fourteen semi-structured interviews over four weeks, both in-person and online, with each interview lasting between 30 and 45 minutes. The participants (six from WP-A, four from WP-B and four from WP-C) were recruited with the help of two WP-A researchers and had different degrees of seniority within their WPs and the Institution, ranging from PhD candidates to post-doctoral researchers and project leaders. The interviews focused on questions aimed at 1) Tracing if and how the value of care became part of the interviewee's work, 2) Understanding how the interviewee thinks about care as a social value in the context of the Institute's mission, and 3) Understanding how care is used as a design guideline in the interviewee's work and the corresponding WP. The data obtained from these interviews, in the form of audio recordings and written notes taken during the interviews, was analysed through thematic analysis ^[50]. The question themes previously described provided the structure for each coding round, with a fourth round added to correlate findings from the transcripts with those from the written notes taken by the first author.

In addition to the interviews, the first author conducted participant observation ^[51] in four group meetings. Two were internal meetings of WP-A aimed at providing space for their PhDs and Postdocs to update each other on their ongoing work and discuss the overall progress of the WP. The third meeting involved WP-A researchers updating project leaders at the Institute level, as well as external stakeholders invested in the Institute's project. The fourth meeting involved researchers from the three work packages that participated in the interviews, plus researchers and project leaders from other WPs and external stakeholders, with the purpose of having PhDs and Postdocs share their progress and challenges concerning both developing care-driven technologies and integrating them in peoples daily routines. These meetings took place in person and online and lasted between 30 and 60 minutes. The data obtained from these meetings is in the form of field notes ^[52], which were interpreted using a narrative analysis method ^[53] and coded following the same structure used for analysing the interviews. Lastly, discourse analysis ^[54] was used to analyse different forms of research and communication materials produced both at a work package and institutional level. These materials ranged from reports and research outputs to newsletters and sections from the official website of the Institute.

6 TRANSLATING CARE

Our findings show that three main challenges affect the fidelity with which the social value of care becomes integrated into technological processes. The first challenge involves packaging the complexity of a social value into a format and language that technical researchers can engage with without decontextualizing the value; we unpack this challenge in the subsection “(understanding) care as an experience.” The second challenge emerges as technical researchers struggle to meaningfully engage with the meaning and purpose of care as an experience rather than an action, which sets in motion different forms of approaching and conceptualizing the value of care that we explore in the subsection (reinterpreting) care as an action. The third challenge concerns translating the action of care into a programming language by technical researchers from work packages B and C, which we examine in the subsection “(embedding) care as a technical property.

6.1 (Understanding) Care as an experience

The translation of care from a social value into a programming language begins as researchers from WP-A seek to capture what care looks like both in practice and as a social value for the ageing population. This work is carried out through diverse forms of empirical research, workshops, and feedback sessions with members of a government-supported patient and public involvement network and with other relevant stakeholders like family members and professional care providers. The findings gathered by WP-A show that the ageing population relies on diverse practices, interactions and emotions to conceptualise care as a value, ranging from a stranger helping with groceries to spending quality time with friends to an unexpected phone call from grandchildren.

While varied, the practices, interactions and emotions that are showing up in WP-A research have in common that they are mostly taking place outside places and situations that are traditionally associated with ageing, such as older adults that are bed-ridden, living with reduced mobility, or that spend their days sitting on a couch watching TV. In reducing later life to a small set of actions and needs, WP-A argues that current narratives of later life promoted by media and many public and private health providers perpetuate an understanding of care in relation to singular actions rather than holistic experiences. The notion that care is an experience that can be understood as an action is of concern for WP-A as it risks reducing care to a singular event that might not reflect the emotional, behavioral, and relational characteristics needed to transform everyday practices into experiences of care. This concern is exemplified in the following scenario provided by a WP-A researcher:

“If I visit my grandmother to keep her company, but she suspects that I don’t really want to be there, she will not feel ‘care’ in the ways that we [WP-A] are showing older adults experience care. But this sort of ‘emotionally empty’ caregiving is often what comes out of the work done by care providers working in public health because they have very little time with each patient and often just sit there and keep them company as nothing more than checking an item from a list. It’s essentially like being a human monitor. But these types of interactions are anyway considered to embody the value of care because, in theory, you could feel care out of them.”

This example raises concerns in two interlinked areas. One has to do with the risks of automatizing and homogenizing care in later living, which can lead to the removal of the lived experiences that turn mundane and unremarkable habits of daily life, like pouring a cup of tea for someone, into an act of care. The other concerns the importance of understanding the context where the ageing population experiences care in order for researchers to scrutinize the value-washing of practices and technologies. In the previous example, the value of care is associated with the action of keeping company, but the main point is that any action already associated with health and medical practices can be disguised as an action embodying the value of care because the public discourse is already there to support such translation. Still, work packages B and C are more interested in how ageing adults conceptualize care as a value when interacting with assistive technologies, care providers and health services rather than through other experiences of daily life.

This is because technical researchers from WPs B and C are working on challenges that are already rooted in specific contexts that were specified by their respective WP leaders before most of the interviewees started their research at the Institute. With no empirical data coming from the work of WP-A to encourage the technical work packages to explore care in non-conventional settings, the current context of research for technical WPs is made up entirely of the worn-out “sites of care” that WP-A warns against, such as bedrooms, couches and bathrooms in care homes and hospitals. Nevertheless, technical researchers (6/8) generally agree that the insights shared by WP-A are helpful for expanding how they think about care-driven technologies, which could have an impact in future projects as long as WP-A can provide them with simple definitions of care that they can efficiently operationalise in their work. As a WP-C researcher explains:

“Everyday life as a context for understanding care is too stochastic to work with. We need to develop technologies that provide care across a wide segment of the population yet within a well-defined probability spectrum. If care is also about a glass of water, then great, I can program that. But I cannot anticipate if the older adult will perceive the glass of water as an act of care or just as a glass of water. So we can either not do it to preserve certain actions from becoming algorithmic and losing meaning or we can do it and guarantee that the person will be hydrated at the expense of feeling care. I think we [in WP-C] all agree that the priority is delivering the glass of water.”

Translating care from an experience to an action is a delicate and contentious area of research for WP-A. On the one hand, there are no formal guidelines to help researchers in WP-A to translate social values into a technical language without the context – places, practices, interactions, manners, gestures, emotions and other aspects that shape care as a social value – being lost in translation. On the other hand, developing those guidelines risks turning the multi-dimensional experience of care described by older adults into a one-dimensional value that fits the technical needs and limitations of current algorithm-driven technologies. In an attempt to find a middle ground, WP-A has been providing technical researchers with stories, reflections, visual material and scenarios of later life that can help them think through, not design through, the value of care as experienced by ageing adults. Yet, technical researchers (8/8) stress that they are not trained to translate complex experiences of care into technical processes that can effectively become part of development stages. Consequently, how the value of care should be translated from context to practice has been left open to the interpretation of researchers in WPs B and C.

6.2 (Reinterpreting) Care as an action

For WP-C, the value of care can be best translated into a technical language by identifying specific events and symptoms that set an action of care in motion. They reason that actions can be programmed, which enables technologies to actively participate in the lives of older adults (within the context of bedrooms, living rooms and bathrooms) and intervene when necessary. For example, if an ageing adult experiences care when surrounded by loved ones, the ability to program a sensor that detects loneliness and sends a notification to the loved ones would result in an act of care. In other words, the sensor enables the unfolding of care practices. This understanding of care through actions such as monitoring, measuring and sensing sees care delivered as an end goal rather than a process, which WP-A warns holds too many similarities with the practice of providing medical treatment. A WP-A researcher shares an example to illustrate their concerns:

“Care is often not medical...Research participants regularly refer to care in relation to small things like, for example, receiving help with carrying groceries up the stairs from a neighbour that they were not familiar with because that kind of care is unexpected and can lead to other forms of care, like casual conversations, or just saying hi to each other when passing by; little things that add up to how an older adult might be experiencing care as part of daily life. If the same action is carried by an assistive technology programmed to help, it is not necessarily perceived as care because care was felt in how the relationship between these neighbours is evolving rather than in the action itself of helping with groceries.”

A WP-A researcher warns that such an approach risks reducing the number of events where an ageing adult experiences care, stressing that there is a thin line between automatizing aspects of care and replacing experiences that older adults associate with care. Yet, WP-C researchers (4/4) stress that they need to understand the action that delivers care rather than where care is delivered in order to use the same technology in multiple settings. The same argument is made by WP-B

researchers (4/4), who stress the need to work with data that can be generalized to a large number of events and conditions, like knowing that between certain ages, older adults are more likely to become dehydrated – an event that WP-C can address by programming a sequence of actions. Still, by conceptualising the value of care as an action, many of the nuances that WP-A aims to instil in the research of technical work packages are lost in translation. The following example is provided:

"Ageing adults will often refer to a family member or friend visiting and doing small things around the house to make sure they are ok, like leaving a glass of water next to them without being inquisitive about how much water they've been drinking. The subtlety with which the water is given seems to matter a lot to them, and the same applies to other everyday things like taking medications, walking for a bit and so on. Now, what happens if you add sensors and cameras and automatize all those experiences into acts, is that you end up removing everything that makes a glass of water an experience of care" [WP-A researcher]

In the example above, what matters for WP-C is that the person is hydrated by the most effective means possible: hydration, whereby the hand of a family member, nurse or robot is the act of care. For WP-A, what matters is that the emotional dimensions of care are not removed from people's lives, so questions of who and why are more important than questions of how. For WP-B, what matters is how you collect enough data to know that after a certain age, event, health episode, and so on, an older adult will be more prone to dehydration, at higher risk of falling, more likely to decay in health due to loneliness, or not strong enough to carry grocery bags or move independently. This data, a WP-B researcher explains, comes from free-text and unstructured patient-generated data, which cannot possibly capture the emotional aspects of care that WP-A aims for them to consider, because:

"The data we work with can provide information such as that after a certain age, older adults are increasingly more prone to fall while going about their everyday life. But we cannot, in its current form, use this data to infer if they distinguish between care and medical attention depending if, for example, a family member, a nurse or a robot comes to provide assistance." [WP-B researcher]

Similar to WP-C, for WP-B the value of care can be best translated into a technical language by identifying specific events and symptoms that need to be quantified and datafied for actions of care to be efficiently delivered. The data that WP-B collects will inform the design of technologies developed by WP-C, which further removes the work of WP-A from the translation of care from context to practice. In turn, care as an action that can be programmed emerges as the common language between technical researchers, privileging how programmers and developers understand the need and delivery of care. At this stage in the translation process, a WP-A researcher warns, if what makes care a social value continues to be diluted, *"there is a danger of care being used in a way which starts to lose so much meaning that it becomes a bit pointless for guiding the design of [assistive] technologies."*

6.3 (Embedding) Care as a technical property

So far, the value of care has been translated from an experience into an action, but for technical work packages to develop care-driven technologies, actions need to be programmed. In the case of WP-B, their researchers (4/4) are quick to stress that they struggle with institutional expectations that care can be embedded in their models because, a WP-B researcher explains, *"we don't have guidelines to help us develop a model that we can confidently say it 'cares' for people in the way that WP-A has shown its needed."* Similarly, another WP-B researcher adds: *"We can't program an algorithm to embody aspects of 'care' in an explicit way as we can do, for example, with privacy."* For WP-B, privacy is a value that can be

easily reduced to a set of instructions because there is a general understanding across disciplines like data science, AI ethics and medicine concerning what privacy means in the context of data and algorithmic behavior. The same can be said for other values that have emerged from technical challenges or have been borrowed from medical principles (such as beneficence and nonmaleficence); technical researchers (8/8) claim to know already how to translate these values into a programming language. However, these researchers contend that the same cannot be said for care as a value because the term doesn't afford that simplicity.

When asked about other mainstream values emerging from the social turn, such as inclusive and fair, researchers in both WPs B and C agree that these are easier to translate into technical properties because, on the one hand, they have more stable definitions than care; therefore it is easier to judge if an algorithm is making decisions that are not inclusive or unfair. On the other hand, researchers agree that social values such as inclusive and fair have a universal meaning, which makes it possible to distil them into sets of instructions through mathematical language. In contrast, care is seen as a highly complex value that holds too many meanings for different people and situations. In other words, care as a value is too unstable to be programmed, at least for now, as WP-C researchers (3/4) claim that it might not be long until other complex social values like care become part of the value-based frameworks guiding the race for AI technologies. Their reasoning is that values like privacy and fairness were as ill-defined and open to interpretation as care is now, however, they became stable and one-dimensional as academic literature, media, and industry adopted them. Their hope is that, as the space of assistive technologies continues to be algorithmically retrofitted, values like care will become as straightforward to implement as those of privacy and fairness.

Yet, while values such as privacy and fairness have been used for a longer time in the design of algorithms, and the computer scientists and engineers we interviewed claim to know how to translate such values into specific instructions that can be programmed, when asked about the steps of this process, technical researchers (8/8) quickly point out that there are no formal guidelines to do so. Instead, the translation of values into technical properties is more about making (often individual) assessments of the algorithm's behaviour in relation to the value being used as a guideline. A WP-C researcher explains this translation in the following way:

“Privacy could be blurring the images my cameras and sensors collect. Then transparency becomes having the capacity to show how the process of privacy works, and then fairness is about showing that we are not selling the data we are anonymising. So, these values are essentially technical properties that will set boundaries to what algorithms can do. The challenge ahead is to understand which technical properties better represent what we understand as care, and what we want the algorithms to do and not do.”

As the social value of care became a technical property, the diverse contexts and practices where ageing adults experience care were lost in translation, but the notion that care as a value can be operationalised as a design guideline remains part of the design strategy of technical work packages. Yet, it is still unclear which actions will be guided, encoded and justified through the value of care as at this stage in the translation process, the meaning and purpose of care is left completely up to the interpretation of those directly involved with the programming of assistive technologies, which excludes the voices of WP-A researchers and the older adults that communicate through their work. Eventually, as technical researchers anticipate, care will be subject to the same processes that turned values such as privacy, fairness and transparency into layers of compliance for developing algorithm-driven technologies. But the question remains, whose understanding of care will those technologies comply with?

7 DISCUSSION

Our research shows that as the value of care is purposefully moved from context to practice, it becomes reinterpreted and appropriated in different ways, not only in terms of what the value of care stands for but the purpose it serves for the goals of each work package. These findings raise concerns regarding the extent to which social values extracted from social contexts and use practices can be meaningfully implemented as design guidelines and, more importantly, show that social values are easily reinterpreted and appropriated as they become translated into technical languages. We discussed these findings in the following subsections.

7.1 From social to technical value

Our research indicates that for social values to become productive during development stages, they need to be translated into technical values. The difference between social and technical values is that the former are nuanced and require that the people using them are knowledgeable of the context in which they emerged. In contrast, technical values are universal^[55] and applicable to all contexts rather than representative of specific contexts. Therefore, for social values to become technical and encompass a larger area of application, they must first be rid of the context from which they emerged. In the case of care, our findings show that the practices from which the value was extracted are not useful for technical researchers. Instead, the actions at the centre of these practices are understood as the drivers of caring practices, whereas the diverse conditions that frame those actions across a wide range of ageing experiences are unaccounted for.

This loss of complexity, as researchers from WPs B and C explained, can be found in other technical values widely used across value-based frameworks, such as fairness, privacy and transparency. Still, despite a wealth of research showing that social values can have vastly different meanings across cultural contexts^[43], the social turn in HCI continues to advocate for diversifying value-based frameworks emerging from technical contexts in favour of bottom-up values such as pluralist, sustainable and inclusive. More so, there is no evidence to argue that social values will not become devoid of contextual meaning as they are appropriated for technical purposes and be readily available for their use as universal values. If the meaning and purpose of a social value are, when it comes to the programming of algorithms, whatever the last programmer thinks it is, then why should we keep investing in making social values part of technological development processes?

This question is particularly relevant when considering that developers seem to see the growing capacity of algorithms to retrofit diverse aspects of everyday life as justifying the need for new guiding values. Our research presents such a case, where the inevitable adoption of algorithms in the context of health and medical applications raises the need for social values, such as “care,” that can nudge people into trusting technologies that, at least for now, do not have a world model that affords them the adaptive capacities needed for providing care. Similar examples can be found in the development of technologies ranging from self-driving cars to large language models and robotics. While social values help researchers think through challenges, the danger lies in translating values into technical properties, where they will become just another addition to an ever-growing list of qualitative values that are used for quantitative purposes.

7.2 Value (mis)alignment

Whereas social values are not reflected in the decision-making processes of algorithms as more than a mere illusion, the social values that become associated with algorithms have a real impact on how people perceive the technologies that allow humans and algorithms to interact^[11]. Therefore, the value of care is more likely to play a role in shaping how the ageing population perceives the impact of assistive technologies than in shaping the behaviour of these technologies. To be clear, the lack of effective guidelines to embed social values into lines of code does not mean that value-based

frameworks cease to be used. On the contrary, regardless of the extent to which algorithms will behave according to the social values they were engineered through, these values are constantly exploited as part of value-washing practices [40,56,57]: *“a scenario in which those producing, purchasing, or using AI systems can ‘ethics shop,’ ‘ethics wash,’ and ‘ethics dump’ without fear of facing any real consequences”* [58].

In other words, value-washing enables those responsible for developing algorithm-driven technologies to frame and legitimise their products and the outcomes of their services through social values rather than explainable and measurable outputs. To be fair, research shows that those involved in value-washing practices are not always aware of the implications that arise from heavily associating algorithmic behaviour with the social values that people rely on to discern good from evil [59]. Instead, value-washing is often the result of developers not having the necessary training and guidelines to determine if algorithms are behaving according to the value of choice. Yet, in the context of value-washing technology, the translation of social values into technical ones has received little attention.

While research has shown that, for better or worse, technical values can play a central role in aligning researchers [60], this alignment can result, on the one hand, in even narrower understandings of a value by building on the experiences and expectations of a small group of researchers. On the other hand, our findings show that when social values such as fairness and privacy become technical and universal, they can be leveraged to give algorithms a false sense of consistency when it comes to researchers judging the capacity of algorithms to make decisions that will affect people's sense of fairness and privacy. Such was the case in how alignment was built across WPs B and C, where researchers described having a shared understanding of what care means based on mainstream definitions of care – the very definitions that WP-A aimed to remove from the design of assistive technologies. Yet, when it came to using care as a guiding value, researchers relied on personal rather than shared understandings of care. This is not to say that researchers are purposefully value-washing technology, but that value-washing is an inevitable outcome of relying on social values because, under the current paradigm, the only way a technology can be embedded with values is by association rather than programming.

7.3 Algorithmic values

When social values become technical properties, they are no longer bound to the experiences of people but to the behaviour of algorithms. In turn, the behaviour of algorithms will become subject to scrutiny as humans interact with them as part of daily life. For example, the ageing adults who will interact with the care-driven technologies developed by the Institution will judge the extent to which these technologies indeed care for them; social values work both ways. This raises additional concerns about the use of value-based frameworks not only to disguise the behaviour of algorithms (value-washing) but also to mediate the public discourse and adoption patterns emerging around them. Despite no evidence that social values are successfully being embedded in code in ways that lead to principled algorithms [59], social values and algorithmic processes will continue to become entangled [10] through the imaginaries of users and developers [61,62]. We put forward the concept of algorithmic values to approach this entanglement as a distinct phenomenon that warrants specific theoretical and methodological approaches.

The concept of algorithmic values aims to keep attention focused on the challenges and harms that the widespread use of value-based frameworks sets in motion, not only during ideation stages, where a narrow group of people will decide which algorithmic values better represent the constraints and potential that a specific algorithm-driven technology should respond to [4], or during development processes, where a larger number of stakeholders will have the agency to add and remove values to address concerns or reinforce interests related to varied, and often conflicting, aspects of design, ethics and performance [39], but beyond the confines of technical research and development where the impact of value-based frameworks is still understudied [11].

Yet, the concept comes with a caveat, as operationalizing the concept of algorithmic values can contribute to perpetuating the malpractice set forward by developers and marketers of explaining and justifying algorithmic behaviour through subjective values that appeal to morals rather than through down-to-earth explanations that appeal to reason. To leverage algorithmic values as a research material without risking further support for their use as a design material, critical researchers must refrain from using them to understand or justify the workings of algorithm-driven technologies. Instead, we suggest focusing on three areas in need of empirical research:

1. Marketing strategies: where algorithmic values will be leveraged to replace knowledge of a technology with a moral positioning towards that technology (i.e. a care-driven technology) as a means to exploit people's reliance on social values to navigate social complexity ^[56,63].
2. Human-algorithm interactions: where diverse user groups are not merely reacting to algorithmic outcomes but are actively developing positions towards algorithms based on the values that have become associated with them ^[11,40], such as caring.
3. Meaning-making practices: where algorithmic values will become associated with changes to diverse aspects of everyday life that unfold alongside the use and impact of algorithm-driven technologies ^[64], such as helping with groceries or pouring a glass of water.

8 CONCLUSION

In the context of the widespread use of value-based frameworks for guiding the design of principled algorithms, the social turn in HCI research has contributed to diversifying which values should be turned into guidelines for deciding how algorithms should process data, interact with people and the environment, and produce outcomes. The shift to social values aims to account for the experiences and desires of users with technologies when programming their behavior rather than on the developer's expectations of how these technologies should behave. Yet, the extent to which social values succeed in bringing the use-context to the development stages is understudied. This paper traces the translation of the social value of care as it becomes reinterpreted in meaning and repurposed in function to become a technical property for developing "care technologies." Our findings show that for care to become operational as a design guideline, it needs to be stripped from the richness of the context where it emerged and reduced into a singular definition that can be easily translated into steps in a programming language. These findings raise pressing concerns about the capacity of value-based frameworks to provide design guidelines that prioritize the needs of users rather than the interests of developers, the extent to which the use of these frameworks supports value-washing practices, and the role that value-based frameworks play in influencing the public discourse and adoption of algorithm-driven technologies. To address these challenges, we put forward the concept of algorithmic values and suggest three areas in need of further examination to map the full extent of value-based frameworks' influence in the algorithmic retrofitting of everyday life.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Anonymized

REFERENCES

- [1] 1. Prem, E. (2023). From ethical AI frameworks to tools: A review of approaches. *AI and Ethics*, 3(3), 699–716. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43681-023-00258-9>
- [2] 2. Manders-Huits, N. (2011). What Values in Design? The Challenge of Incorporating Moral Values into Design. *Science and Engineering Ethics*, 17(2), 271–287. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-010-9198-2>

- [3] 3. Knowles, B., Fledderjohann, J., Richards, J. T., & Varshney, K. R. (2023). Trustworthy AI and the Logics of Intersectional Resistance. *Proceedings of the 2023 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*, 172–182. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3593013.3593986>
- [4] 4. Wu, S. T.-I., Demetriou, D., & Husain, R. A. (2023). Honor Ethics: The Challenge of Globalizing Value Alignment in AI. *2023 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*, 593–602. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3593013.3594026>
- [5] 5. Selbst, A. D., Boyd, D., Friedler, S. A., Venkatasubramanian, S., & Vertesi, J. (2019). Fairness and Abstraction in Sociotechnical Systems. *Proceedings of the Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*, 59–68. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3287560.3287598>
- [6] 6. Beer, D. (2017). The social power of algorithms. *Information, Communication & Society*, 20(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2016.1216147>
- [7] 7. Seaver, N. (2018). What Should an Anthropology of Algorithms Do? *Cultural Anthropology*, 33(3), 375–385. <https://doi.org/10.14506/ca33.3.04>
- [8] 8. Mittelstadt, B. D., Allo, P., Taddeo, M., Wachter, S., & Floridi, L. (2016). The ethics of algorithms: Mapping the debate. *Big Data & Society*, 3(2), 2053951716679679. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951716679679>
- [9] 9. Sorenson, J. (2019). Toward a pragmatic and social engineering ethics: Ethnography as provocation. *Paladyn, Journal of Behavioral Robotics*, 10(1), 207–218. <https://doi.org/10.1515/pjbr-2019-0018>
- [10] 10. Rieder, B., Gordon, G., & Sileno, G. (2022). Mapping Value(s) in AI: Methodological Directions for Examining Normativity in Complex Technical Systems. *Sociologica*, 16(3), Article 3. <https://doi.org/10.6092/issn.1971-8853/15910>
- [11] 11. Garnham, I., & Smith, R. C. (2023). The Social Life of Algorithms: Tracing Notions of Algorithms Beyond Human-Algorithm Interactions. In H. Mori, Y. Asahi, A. Coman, S. Vasilache, & M. Rauterberg (Eds.), *HCI International 2023 – Late Breaking Papers* (pp. 273–289). Springer Nature Switzerland. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-48044-7_20
- [12] 12. DeVito, M. A., Birnholtz, J., Hancock, J. T., French, M., & Liu, S. (2018). How People Form Folk Theories of Social Media Feeds and What it Means for How We Study Self-Presentation. *Proceedings of the 2018 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3173574.3173694>
- [13] 13. Lomborg, S., & Kapsch, P. H. (2020). Decoding algorithms. *Media, Culture & Society*, 42(5), 745–761. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0163443719855301>
- [14] 14. Striphas, T., Hallinan, B., Reynolds, C., Brown, M., & Postigo, H. (2021). ALGORITHMIC IMAGINATIONS: RETHINKING “ALGORITHMIC” AS A HEURISTIC FOR UNDERSTANDING COMPUTATIONALLY-STRUCTURED CULTURE. *AoIR Selected Papers of Internet Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5210/spir.v2021i0.12131>
- [15] 15. Kearns, M., & Roth, A. (2019). *The Ethical Algorithm: The Science of Socially Aware Algorithm Design*. Oxford University Press.
- [16] 16. Friedman, B., & Kahn, P. H. (1992). Human agency and responsible computing: Implications for computer system design. *Journal of Systems and Software*, 17(1), 7–14. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0164-1212\(92\)90075-U](https://doi.org/10.1016/0164-1212(92)90075-U)
- [17] 17. Friedman, B., Harbers, M., Hendry, D. G., van den Hoven, J., Jonker, C., & Logler, N. (2021). Eight grand challenges for value sensitive design from the 2016 Lorentz workshop. *Ethics and Information Technology*, 23(1), 5–16. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10676-021-09586-y>
- [18] 18. Appadurai, A. (1988). *The Social Life of Things* [Cambridge Books]. Cambridge University Press. <https://econpapers.repec.org/bookchap/cupcebooks/9780521357265.htm>
- [19] 19. Agha, A. (2003). The social life of cultural value. *Language & Communication*, 23(3–4), 231–273. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0271-5309\(03\)00012-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0271-5309(03)00012-0)
- [20] 20. Friedman, B., & Hendry, D. G. (2019). *Value Sensitive Design: Shaping Technology with Moral Imagination*. MIT Press.
- [21] 21. Simon, J., Wong, P.-H., & Rieder, G. (2020). Algorithmic bias and the Value Sensitive Design approach. *Internet Policy Review*, 9(4). <https://policyreview.info/concepts/algorithmic-bias>
- [22] 22. Morley, J., Floridi, L., Kinsey, L., & Elhalal, A. (2020). From What to How: An Initial Review of Publicly Available AI Ethics Tools, Methods and Research to Translate Principles into Practices. *Science and Engineering Ethics*, 26(4), 2141–2168. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-019-00165-5>
- [23] 23. Schiff, D., Rakova, B., Ayesh, A., Fanti, A., & Lennon, M. (2020). *Principles to Practices for Responsible AI: Closing the Gap* (arXiv:2006.04707). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2006.04707>
- [24] 24. Shneiderman, B. (2022). *Human-Centered AI*. Oxford University Press.
- [25] 25. Jobin, A., Ienca, M., & Vayena, E. (2019). Artificial Intelligence: The global landscape of ethics guidelines. *Nature Machine Intelligence*, 1(9), 389–399. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42256-019-0088-2>
- [26] 26. Floridi, L., Cows, J., Beltrametti, M., Chatila, R., Chazerand, P., Dignum, V., Luetge, C., Madelin, R., Pagallo, U., & Rossi, F. (2021). An ethical framework for a good AI society: Opportunities, risks, principles, and recommendations. *Ethics, Governance, and Policies in Artificial Intelligence*, 19–39.
- [27] 27. Shin, D., & Park, Y. J. (2019). Role of fairness, accountability, and transparency in algorithmic affordance. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 98, 277–284. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2019.04.019>
- [28] 28. Mulgan, G., Breckon, J., Tarrega, M., Bakhshi, H., Davies, J., Khan, H., & Finnis, A. (2019). *Public value: How can it be measured, managed and grown?* (United Kingdom) [Report]. Nesta. <https://apo.org.au/node/240166>
- [29] 29. Corbett-Davies, S., Gaebler, J. D., Nilforoshan, H., Shroff, R., & Goel, S. (2024). The measure and mismeasure of fairness. *The Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 24(1), 312:14730-312:14846.
- [30] 30. *Black in AI*. (n.d.). Retrieved April 24, 2024, from <https://blackinai.github.io/#/>
- [31] 31. Abdilla, A., Arista, N., Baker, K., Benesiinaabandan, S., Brown, M., Cheung, M., Coleman, M., Cordes, A., Davison, J., Duncan, K., Garzon, S., Harrell, D. F., Jones, P.-L., Kealiikanakaoleohaililani, K., Kelleher, M., Kite, S., Lagon, O., Leigh, J., Levesque, M., ... Whaanga, H. (2020). *Indigenous*

- [32] 32. Coskun, A., Cila, N., Nicenboim, I., Frauenberger, C., Wakkary, R., Hassenzahl, M., Mancini, C., Giaccardi, E., & Forlano, L. (2022). More-than-human Concepts, Methodologies, and Practices in HCI. *Extended Abstracts of the 2022 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3491101.3516503>
- [33] 33. Benjamin, R. (2019). *Race after technology: Abolitionist tools for the new Jim Code*. Polity Press.
- [34] 34. Birhane, A. (2020). Algorithmic Colonization of Africa. *SCRIPT-Ed*, 17(2), 389–409. <https://doi.org/10.2966/scrip.170220.389>
- [35] 35. Peters, D., Vold, K., Robinson, D., & Calvo, R. A. (2020). Responsible AI—Two Frameworks for Ethical Design Practice. *IEEE Transactions on Technology and Society*, 1(1), 34–47. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TTS.2020.2974991>
- [36] 36. Orr, W., & Davis, J. L. (2020). Attributions of ethical responsibility by Artificial Intelligence practitioners. *Information, Communication & Society*, 23(5), 719–735. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2020.1713842>
- [37] 37. Morley, J., Elhalal, A., Garcia, F., Kinsey, L., Mökander, J., & Floridi, L. (2021). Ethics as a Service: A Pragmatic Operationalisation of AI Ethics. *Minds and Machines*, 31(2), 239–256. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11023-021-09563-w>
- [38] 38. Kasirzadeh, A. (2021). *Reasons, Values, Stakeholders: A Philosophical Framework for Explainable Artificial Intelligence* (arXiv:2103.00752). arXiv. <http://arxiv.org/abs/2103.00752>
- [39] 39. Varanasi, R. A., & Goyal, N. (2023). “It is currently hodgepodge”: Examining AI/ML Practitioners’ Challenges during Co-production of Responsible AI Values. *Proceedings of the 2023 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3544548.3580903>
- [40] 40. van Maanen, G. (2022). AI Ethics, Ethics Washing, and the Need to Politicize Data Ethics. *Digital Society*, 1(2), 9. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44206-022-00013-3>
- [41] 41. Boyd, K. (2022). Designing Up with Value-Sensitive Design: Building a Field Guide for Ethical ML Development. *Proceedings of the 2022 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*, 2069–2082. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3531146.3534626>
- [42] 42. van Berkel, N., Tag, B., Goncalves, J., & Hosio, S. (2022). Human-centred artificial intelligence: A contextual morality perspective. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 41(3), 502–518. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0144929X.2020.1818828>
- [43] 43. Greene, D., Hoffmann, A. L., & Stark, L. (n.d.). *Better, Nicer, Clearer, Fairer: A Critical Assessment of the Movement for Ethical Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning*.
- [44] 44. Binns, R. (2018). Fairness in Machine Learning: Lessons from Political Philosophy. *Proceedings of the 1st Conference on Fairness, Accountability and Transparency*, 149–159. <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v81/binns18a.html>
- [45] 45. Jakesch, M., Bućinca, Z., Amershi, S., & Olteanu, A. (2022). How Different Groups Prioritize Ethical Values for Responsible AI. *Proceedings of the 2022 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*, 310–323. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3531146.3533097>
- [46] 46. Verma, S., & Rubin, J. (2018). Fairness definitions explained. *Proceedings of the International Workshop on Software Fairness*, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3194770.3194776>
- [47] 47. Chouldechova, A., & G’Sell, M. (2017). *Fairer and more accurate, but for whom?* (arXiv:1707.00046). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1707.00046>
- [48] 48. Seymour, W., Van Kleek, M., Binns, R., & Murray-Rust, D. (2022). Respect as a Lens for the Design of AI Systems. *Proceedings of the 2022 AAAI/ACM Conference on AI, Ethics, and Society*, 641–652. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3514094.3534186>
- [49] 49. Klenk, M. (2021). How Do Technological Artefacts Embody Moral Values? *Philosophy & Technology*, 34(3), 525–544. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13347-020-00401-y>
- [50] 50. Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2022). Conceptual and design thinking for thematic analysis. *Qualitative Psychology*, 9(1), 3–26. <https://doi.org/10.1037/qap0000196>
- [51] 51. Gunn, W., & Løgstrup, L. B. (2014). Participant observation, anthropology methodology and design anthropology research inquiry. *Arts and Humanities in Higher Education*, 13(4), 428–442. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1474022214543874>
- [52] 52. Phillippi, J., & Lauderdale, J. (2018). A Guide to Field Notes for Qualitative Research: Context and Conversation. *Qualitative Health Research*, 28(3), 381–388. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732317697102>
- [53] 53. Cortazzi, M. (1994). Narrative analysis. *Language Teaching*, 27(3), 157–170. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0261444800007801>
- [54] 54. Gee, J. P. (2014). *An Introduction to Discourse Analysis: Theory and Method* (4th ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315819679>
- [55] 55. Schwartz, M. S. (2002). A Code of Ethics for Corporate Code of Ethics. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 41(1), 27–43. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1021393904930>
- [56] 56. Birhane, A., Kalluri, P., Card, D., Agnew, W., Dotan, R., & Bao, M. (2022). The Values Encoded in Machine Learning Research. *Proceedings of the 2022 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*, 173–184. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3531146.3533083>
- [57] 57. Bietti, E. (2020). From ethics washing to ethics bashing: A view on tech ethics from within moral philosophy. *Proceedings of the 2020 Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*, 210–219. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3351095.3372860>
- [58] 58. Floridi, L. (2019). Translating Principles into Practices of Digital Ethics: Five Risks of Being Unethical. *Philosophy & Technology*, 32(2), 185–193. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13347-019-00354-x>
- [59] 59. Morley, J., Kinsey, L., Elhalal, A., Garcia, F., Ziosi, M., & Floridi, L. (2023). Operationalising AI ethics: Barriers, enablers and next steps. *AI & SOCIETY*, 38(1), 411–423. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-021-01308-8>
- [60] 60. Floridi, L., & Cows, J. (2019). A Unified Framework of Five Principles for AI in Society. *Harvard Data Science Review*, 1(1).

<https://doi.org/10.1162/99608f92.8cd550d1>

- [61] 61. Bucher, T. (2017). The algorithmic imaginary: Exploring the ordinary affects of Facebook algorithms. *Information, Communication & Society*, 20(1), 30–44. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2016.1154086>
- [62] 62. Ytre-Arne, B., & Moe, H. (2021). Folk theories of algorithms: Understanding digital irritation. *Media, Culture & Society*, 43(5), 807–824. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0163443720972314>
- [63] 63. Danaher, J., & Sætra, H. S. (2022). Technology and moral change: The transformation of truth and trust. *Ethics and Information Technology*, 24(3), 35. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10676-022-09661-y>
- [64] 64. Anonymised, Forthcoming